

USING NEWSOLA TO SUPPORT READING AND WRITING

¹Joshua Belknap; ²Dao Tran; ³Cynthia S. Wiseman, EdD

²Pham Van Dong University, Quang Ngai, Vietnam

³Borough of Manhattan Community College City University of New York, NY, USA

Email: ¹jbelknap@bmcc.cuny.edu; ²maidaoqn@gmail.com; ³cwiseman@bmcc.cuny.edu

ABSTRACT

Web-based software or mobile apps can support the development of reading and writing in the EFL/ESL classroom. Online resources like Newsela or CommonLit, instructional content platforms web-based software/app, can facilitate individualized instruction and independent reading to support the development of reading and writing in the ESL classroom. This presentation introduced Newsela and comparable apps and provided suggestions for implementation, such as assigning level-appropriate articles, customizing writing prompts, and reviewing and responding to student work.

Key words: Reading and Technology, Assessment, Individualized Instruction, Independent Reading, Embedded Assignments, Differentiated Instruction, Digital Instructional Content Platform

1 WEB-BASED PLATFORMS/APPS IN EDUCATION

Most educators would agree that the World Wide Web (WWW), a decentralized information system in which anyone can add or access new information, including news articles and teaching materials, has enhanced the role of technology in education (Sife, Lwoga, & Sanga, 2007). In the last decades supplemental use of Information and Computer Technologies (ICTs), i.e., web-based platforms and mobile apps, such as blogs, wikis, learning management systems, podcasting, and mobile apps, have been routinely implemented to complement the traditional classroom. (Arabasz and Baker, 2003). Indeed, some would argue that these web-based tools, which provide information access and facilitate communication, have assumed a critical role in education as they are increasingly viewed as useful in fostering collaboration and encouraging socialization in the learning environment. Wiseman and Belknap (2013) contend that the use of these web-based tools contribute to what Vygotsky (1962) called the co-construction of knowledge, a dynamic collaborative process that facilitates language acquisition in the language classroom.

In the ESL/EFL classroom, web-based platforms and apps have become increasingly popular to facilitate individualized instruction and independent reading to develop fluency and comprehension in reading. In Individualized instruction, which focuses on the needs of the individual student, teaching is specific and targets one need at a time. Teachers help second language learners who are low proficiency, to understand and learn while other students of higher

proficiency can skip topics they already know and go on to advanced information. ²Online resources such as Newsela which offer thousands of articles across a broad range of topics and levels, support this individualized instruction model.

Independent reading is another strategy that has been effectively used in the second language classroom to support reading in the target language (Sanden, 2012, McGlenn & Parrish, 2002). In the independent reading model, reading is voluntary (Krashen, 1993). It reflects the reader's personal choice of content as well as time and place to read and it is the reading that students choose to do either for information or pleasure (Cullinan, 2000). Access to authentic content enriches the curriculum and can motivate and engage learners in speaking, reading, and writing about current and relevant topics of interest and concern. Platforms like Newsela with a broad range of topics also offer free or low-cost remote access at from multiple devices for more students so that learners are supported in independent reading outside the classroom or even in projects that allow student choice of readings. Apps like www.Newsela.com and www.CommonLit.com, which offer free subscriptions, have become popular in K-12 mainstream classes and all levels of ESL/EFL classrooms to support individualized instruction and independent reading, which promote second language acquisition and literacy.

It is important to note that there is evidence that frequent reading is one factor that contributes to the development of fluency and evidence to suggest that fluency and comprehension are correlated. Indeed one model of fluency instruction in the classroom is Rasinski&Pakak's Fluency Development Lessons (FDL). This model lesson plan is based on several key principles for fluency development, including repeated readings of the text, cueing phrase boundaries in texts, and providing students with easy reading materials. The FDL can be used daily and results have shown substantial improvement in reading rate of second graders (Rasinski&Padak, 1994). Easy low-cost access to a wide variety of current, adapted readings offered by Newsela and sites like it can thus support frequent reading which contributes to fluency and comprehension.

1.1 Newsela

Newsela is a web-based platform/app designed to enrich curricula with embedded assignments or provide a repository of articles for independent reading and individualized instruction. Newsela offers a basic free subscription with a Pro version available at a monthly subscription rate for institutions or individuals; according to Newsela's website, anyone can join Newsela as a student to read articles and complete quizzes, writing responses, annotations, and Power Words activities. Newsela offers over 6000 news articles from respected news sources such as the *Washington Post*, *Scientific American* and *Smithsonian.com.*, with reading activities at five different reading levels.

This program offers thematic text-sets across disciplines and targets various skills, e.g., cultivating close reading. With Newsela, teachers can, for example, customize writing prompts or

² (Retrieved from =<https://www.understood.org/en/school-learning/partnering-with-childs-school/instructional-strategies/individualized-instruction-vs-differentiated-instruction>)

facilitate close reading with software-generated feedback. It is also possible to print articles, quizzes, and answer keys for use in-class.

In a nutshell, Newsela is an instructor resource for building student reading comprehension using nonfiction, e.g., current events, historical writings, and biographies. Educators can assign readings with instructions for their class. Through easy access to authentic articles that are current and relevant, Newsela encourages close reading, critical thinking, and participation in and engagement with conversations about urgent topics.

1.2 Features of Newsela

Readings Adapted across Reading Levels

Newsela is adaptive. Each Newsela article is available at five reading levels. For any article, students can click on the leveling button above the title to see and navigate between all levels. (see Fig. 1) The program creates customized reading levels for students over time and presents them with reading passages at the appropriate reading level. However, students can decide to read articles and complete quizzes at any reading level and at multiple levels for the same article.

Figure 1: Newsela reading levels

Articles from Primary Sources

Newsela offers access to seminal historical documents in the primary sources library, including The Declaration of Independence, Martin Luther King Jr.'s Letter from the Birmingham Jail and Herodotus on Making of a Mummy, as well as biographies of influential people and famous

speeches. (see Fig. 2) The site’s primary sources are offered at different reading levels, modified or unaltered depending on the level.

GOV. & ECON. ⚡ ES ❤️ 567
Primary Sources: The Constitution of the United States of America

U.S. HISTORY ⚡ ES ❤️ 290
Primary Sources: Civil Rights Act of 1964

GOV. & ECON. ⚡ ES ❤️ 434
Primary Sources: The Bill of Rights

U.S. HISTORY ⚡ ❤️ 170
Primary Sources: The Monroe Doctrine

U.S. HISTORY ⚡ ❤️ 297
Primary Sources: Jefferson's Message on the Lewis & Clark Expedition

U.S. HISTORY ⚡ ES ❤️ 234
Primary Sources: Brown v. Board of Education

Figure 2: Primary Source Materials

Thematic Text Sets

Newsela’s database of readings includes theme-specific sets of articles that students and instructors can access (See Fig. 3). In addition, instructors can create their own “text set” with articles they curate on the site, so that students can read nine or more articles on the same topic. Research indicates that the use of conceptually coherent text sets is effective in building vocabulary and knowledge, as well as preparing students for critically reading new texts on the same topic (Cervetti, Wright, & Hwang, 2016). Broad knowledge and topic-specific knowledge are both requisites for reading comprehension. Moreover, background knowledge enables readers to make inferences, which aids in comprehension, critical thinking and memory. Studies have also shown that prior knowledge of a topic has a greater impact on reading comprehension than generalized reading ability (Tracy, Menickelli, & Scales, 2017; Willingham, 2006).

FEATURED TEXT SETS

Figure 3: Thematic Text Sets

Assessment

Newsela provides comprehension quizzes that generate data for each individual student and can be used for formative assessment. (See Fig. 4.) Assessments are integrated directly into articles to help students engage with the content and to give teachers practical insights on students' activity to work into curriculum. Differentiated, high-interest texts that are organized by content area and aligned to course topics will engage readers more.

Figure 4: Lexile levels, formative assessment quizzes

1.3 Ideas for instruction with Newsela

Independent reading and reading groups

Newsela allows instructors to assign learners a reading that is adapted across five different levels. Students can elect to read the passage at the Lexile level (reading level) appropriate for them. Instructors/learners can print the readings out, or read them in a computer lab or on phones/devices in the classroom or at home. In class, students, who read the article at their individual reading level, are better prepared to discuss the content of the passage.

Aside from encouraging independent reading outside class, educators can utilize Newsela in-class. For example, instructors can create class reading groups and assign students a code to join their particular group. The Instructor then can assign articles to the students in the group, customize instructions for a particular reading assignment, ask questions through annotations, and customize writing prompts following the reading. As Newsela offers the same article at 5 different levels, students (or teachers) can choose the appropriate level to facilitate their reading comprehension.

Formative assessment and analytics

Newsela provides short quizzes about any article. After reading, students can test themselves using the comprehension quiz either provided by Newsela or created by the instructor. Quizzes target certain reading skills: Close reading, central idea for gist or summarizing, analysis of development of ideas or themes, interpreting vocabulary in context; analyzing the structure of texts and determining point of view and purpose. In addition to comprehension quizzes, Newsela offers assessment tools such as annotations, writing prompts, and analytics. All Newsela reading passages have writing prompts that students can respond to in the activities panel, or instructors can create their own writing prompts if they prefer. The paid-subscription Pro version of Newsela also provides analytics to track and evaluate students' performance over time. With Newsela Pro, teachers are able to view student progress printable reports sorted by class, individual student, or reading passage. Newsela Pro provides analytic reports of student progress that instructors can share with administrators.

Annotation of Texts

Newsela allows students and teachers to read, highlight, and annotate texts (See Fig. 5). Students and instructors can also discuss or dialogue through sharing their annotations about the reading, e.g., questions about vocabulary or comment or opinions about the article. Using these annotation dialogue windows, teachers can review and respond to student work. Student and instructor annotations appear only at the reading level at which they are posted and shared. In addition to annotation dialogues, instructors can also annotate the reading passages themselves, and students can write free responses, enabling them to further practice their writing skills. Instructors are then able to respond to both student annotations and their free responses.

Figure 5: Text highlighting and annotation

2 CONCLUSION

Web-based platforms or mobile apps are important resources in today's second language classroom. When used to supplement in-class reading activities such as reading groups or individualized instruction or out of class independent reading programs, online resources like Newsela can support the development of reading skills, which furthers second language acquisition. Newsela can help students build reading comprehension through leveled articles, real-time assessments, and insights for instructors to shape curricula. The reading passages on Newsela are designed to help develop nonfiction fluency and critical-thinking skills necessary for students to comprehend and critically engage with news and informational texts in English.

REFERENCES

- [1] Arabasz, P. and Baker, M. B. (2003) Evolving Campus Support Models for E-Learning Courses. <http://www.educause.edu/ir/library/pdf/ERS0303/ekf0303.pdf> accessed 11 November, 2006.
- [3] Cervetti, G. N., Wright, T. S., & Hwang, H. (2016). Conceptual coherence, comprehension, and vocabulary acquisition: A knowledge effect? *Reading and Writing*, 29(4), 761-779.
- [4] Cullinan, B.E., (2000). Independent reading and school achievement. *School Library Media Research, Research Journal of the American Association of School Librarians*, 3. Retrieved October 1, 2018 from: http://www.ala.org/aasl/sites/ala.org.aasl/files/content/aaslpubsandjournals/slr/vol13/SLMR_IndependentReading_V3.pdf

- [5] Krashen, S. 1993. *The power of reading: Insights from the research*. Englewood, Colo.: Libraries Unlimited.
- [6] McGlenn, J. M., & Parrish, A. (2002). Accelerating ESL students' reading progress with accelerated reader. *Reading Horizons*, 42(3), 2.
- [7] Rasinski, T. & Padak, N. (1994). Effects of fluency development on urban second-grade readers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 87, 158-165.
- [8] Sanden, S. (2012). Independent reading: Perspectives and practices of highly effective teachers. *The Reading Teacher*, 66(3), 222-231.
- [9] Sife, A., Lwoga, E. & Sanga, C. (2007). New technologies for teaching and learning: Challenges for higher learning institutions in developing countries. *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 3(2), 57-67. Open Campus, The University of the West Indies, West Indies. Retrieved October 6, 2018 from: <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/42360/>.
- [10] Tracy, K. N., Menickelli, K., & Scales, R. Q. (2017). Courageous Voices: Using Text Sets to Inspire Change. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 60(5), 527-536.
- [11] Vgotsky, L.S. (1962). *Thought and language*. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- [12] Washington, DC: National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education. at <http://ncee.ed.gov>
- [13] Willingham, D. T. (2006). How knowledge helps. *American Educator*, 30(1), 30-37.
- [14] Wiseman, C. & Belknap, J. (2013). Wikis: A Knowledge Platform for Collaborative Learning in ESL Reading. *TESOL Journal*, 4(2), 359-369.